

Tariffs to ideas?

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U.S. trade policy raises fears of deepening the global poverty crisis. Since April 2, 2025, after announcing a universal 10% tax on its imports, market reactions have been occurring that tend to worsen growth forecasts and, as is often the case, with greater harmful impacts on weak countries.

The effectiveness of protectionism for domestic industries is debated because there is evidence that it does not benefit consumers or create robust production systems. Moreover, breaking agreements and interrupting dialogues does not favour the quality of goods and services.

At the heart of the slogan "Make America Great Again" is the absence of the other, of diversity, because the standards of the one who is thought to be more powerful are being forced.

The identification of efficient processes or the creation of formulas that allow lower manufacturing costs are the result of innovative ideas. In other words, when a barrier is erected to "protect" higher cost methods, it is basically punishing opinions, those who think differently, and alienating people who seek better living conditions for all.

President Trump's "Liberation Day" adds other episodes that show that the rejection of the poor people of the "global south", expansionism and plutocracy would be the basis of a new era. But there is always hope because one cannot deny the inalienable rights of the human being, and ignore that expression, communication, the voice of minorities define people and give meaning to existence.